

Optimizing Nature's Blueprint: Comparative Study of Hybrid Algorithms for Terrain Features Extraction

¹Chandrakiran Reddy Kasireddy, ²Sai Theja Kunta, ³Srihitha Jindam

⁴Dr. Sake Madhu

^{1,2,3}Student, ⁴Professor & Head of Department -AI&ML
^{1,2,3,4}Guru Nanak Institutions Technical Campus, Ibrahimpatnam

Abstract—Extraction of terrain features is a significant conduct with many uses across numerous sectors. This research paper provides a comparative study of three nature-inspired algorithms for extraction of terrain features: the hybrid algorithm PBBO (Union of Biogeography-Based Optimization called as BBO and Particle Swarm Optimization called PSO), the fusion of Biogeography-Based Optimization and Artificial Bee Colony, and the third algorithm which is Hybrid Flower Pollination by Artificial Bees called as FPAB/Biogeography-Based Optimization. We are going to do a thorough comparative analysis to validate the performance of multiple algorithms in this research. We use criteria for evaluation like the kappa coefficient and accuracy to rate the algorithms' efficiency and predictability. The PBBO algorithm develops an optimized and reliable optimization strategy by combining the best qualities of PSO and BBO. Likewise, we combine BBO with ABC making it a hybrid algorithm, to improve the performance of BBO by applying ABC's clustering capabilities. We generate incredibly accurate results in satellite image classification by using flower pollination by artificial bees for data clustering and BBO for classification. The results of the comparative study of these three nature-inspired algorithms advance terrain analysis and support accurate and efficient decision-making spanning a range of applications.

Index Terms— Particle Swarm Optimization, Biogeography-Based Optimization (BBO), Genetic Algorithms, Hybrid swarm intelligence, Artificial Bee Colony (ABC), Flower Pollination by Artificial Bees, Satellite Image Classification, Terrain features, Kappa Coefficient.

I. INTRODUCTION

The extraction of important information made possible by satellite image categorization can improve remote sensing applications like land cover study results, environmental monitoring, and urban planning [1]. Researchers have used algorithms inspired by nature that replicate the collective behavior and optimization techniques seen in natural systems to increase the accuracy and effectiveness of this process. This paper serves as a thorough comparison of three well-known nature-inspired algorithms: PBBO (Particle Swarm Optimisation and Biogeography-Based Optimisation hybrid algorithm) [2], ABC/BBO (Hybrid Flower Pollination by Artificial Bees and Biogeography-Based Optimization) [3], and FPAB/BBO[4].

The Particle Swarm Optimization and Biogeography-Based Optimization properties are combined in the PBBO algorithm [2]. The goal of PBBO is to improve efficiency and optimization for satellite image categorization through the integration of these techniques [2]. By combining BBO and ABC, a novel approach is introduced to enhance BBO's performance by taking into account the behavior of bees from the Artificial Bee Colony algorithm [3]. The fusion technique delivers superior optimization results and permits precise identification of natural terrain characteristics by adding ABC, which specializes in clustering [3]. Another hybrid algorithm, FPAB/BBO, combines the ideas of BBO and artificial bee flower pollination [3]. In this method, information from satellite images is clustered with data clustering methods based on false bees pollinating flowers. BBO is then used for further classification, producing extremely accurate outcomes for satellite image analysis [4].

This research uses the kappa coefficient and accuracy measurements as evaluation metrics for assessing the performance of these three algorithms [2][3][4]. The agreement between predicted and reference classifications is measured by the kappa coefficient, which sheds light on the reliability and accuracy of the algorithms. The comparison study's main goal is to validate the efficiency and evaluate the performance of the PBBO, BBO, ABC fusion, and FPAB/BBO algorithms for extracting terrain features from satellite data. The above techniques can be chosen and used for satellite image classification tasks after a thorough examination of and comparison of their performance outcomes.

This paper explains the comparative study of PBBO, a fusion of BBO [5] and ABC, and FPAB/BBO algorithms in great depth in the parts that follow. A discussion of the findings and analysis follows the presentation of the technique and experimental accomplishing utilized to determine these algorithms' performance. The report comes to a close with a summary of the results and possibilities for additional research.

Natural Computing

Natural computing is a branch of study that designs and creates computational models and algorithms by taking insights from natural systems and phenomena. It examines the computational capabilities and principles found in nature and aspires to make use of them to address challenging issues across a wide variety of sectors. In natural computing simulation of biological systems and processes is an essential part. Evolutionary algorithms, like genetic algorithms, mimic the process of natural selection and evolution by iteratively generating a population of different approaches to optimize solutions.

Swarm intelligence is another branch of natural computing that resembles the group behavior of social insect colonies, bird flocks, or fish schools [6]. These systems' self-organization and collaboration are the building blocks for algorithms like particle swarm optimization and Ant Colony Optimization (ACO). To find the most effective responses in a complicated issue space, they

make use of the group's collective intelligence. Biologically inspired algorithms also contain principles derived from nature, such as immune-inspired algorithms, which are motivated by the immune system's capacity to recognize and destroy infections, and simulated annealing, which imitates the cooling process in metallurgy to optimize solutions.

Due to its capability to resolve difficult optimization issues, machine learning problems, and other practical problems, the study of natural computing has prompted a lot of interest. To create more effective, reliable, and adaptive algorithms, researchers are integrating computational methods with ideas from biology and other natural systems.

Alwar, an area in Rajasthan, India, was used for this study because of its wide range of characteristics. Barren ground, rocky terrain, vegetation, urban regions, and water bodies are among the feature classifications found here.

Image Classification

Image classification, which desires to give predetermined labels to pictures based on their visual characteristics, is crucial to computer vision [7]. Researchers used the field of natural computing to deal with the complexity of this problem. Natural computing methods which include evolutionary algorithms, neural networks, and swarm intelligence have been used to strengthen image classification skills by drawing inspiration from biological systems. With the objective to create more reliable, effective, and innovative algorithms, researchers are combining natural computing techniques into image classification. Those techniques have been used in a variety of fields, such as remote sensing [1], natural terrain characteristics, and satellite images.

II. RELATED WORK

In the domain of satellite image analysis and terrain feature extraction, several notable contributions and techniques have emerged. This section provides an overview of relevant studies and methodologies, with a focus on research incorporating biologically inspired algorithms.

In the larger context of Biogeography-Based Optimization, Ma (2009) conducted a perceptive examination of migration models. BBO is renowned for its effectiveness in optimization problems and was motivated by biogeographic principles (Simon, 2008). Ma's research explores the behavior of migration models within BBO, illuminating the optimization procedure and advancing our understanding of this technique that takes its cues from nature (Ma, 2009).

A comprehensive description of image classification algorithms used in remote sensing satellite image processing was provided by Sowmya et al. (2017). With a focus on machine learning-based techniques, their study served as an invaluable resource for understanding the various methodologies utilized in the interpretation of satellite imagery. The use of machine learning in satellite image analysis is based on the results of this survey (Sowmya et al., 2017).

Using geostatistical approaches and satellite image processing, Karnieli et al. (2008) focused on evaluating change in land-cover and degeneration in deserts of Central Asia. An illustration of how satellite imagery analysis could be used to monitor changes in the environment in everyday situations was shown. Their work brought attention to the value of satellite data for environmental research and land-use evaluations (Karnieli et al., 2008).

Using plate tectonics and biogeography-based optimization (BBO), Goel et al. (2012) evolved a novel method for extracting water bodies from satellite images. Their method demonstrated improved accuracy in recognizing water bodies within satellite imagery by utilizing the BBO principles and adding geophysical considerations. This combination of biogeography and geophysics demonstrates the adaptability of algorithms drawn from nature for tackling practical issues.

In order to analyze satellite images, Asokan and Anitha (2019) conducted a survey on machine learning-based image processing methods. Their study brought to light the growing interest in using machine learning for feature extraction and categorization in satellite images. Researchers looking at the relationship between machine learning and remote sensing will find this survey to be a useful resource (Asokan & Anitha, 2019).

In conclusion, a variety of strategies and procedures are used in the related work in the fields of terrain feature extraction and satellite image analysis. The thorough survey of image processing methods by Sowmya et al., the environmental monitoring study by Karnieli et al., and Ma's analysis of migration models in BBO all add to the body of knowledge in this field. Asokan and Anitha's survey on machine learning-based approaches and Goel et al.'s combination of BBO and geophysics for water body extraction both highlight the ongoing improvements in the use of nature-inspired algorithms and machine learning to analyze satellite images (Ma, 2009; Sowmya et al., 2017; Karnieli et al., 2008; Goel et al., 2012; Asokan & Anitha, 2019).

Collectively, these works highlight the importance of using nature-inspired and machine learning algorithms to enhance the precision and effectiveness of terrain feature extraction from satellite imagery, expanding the field's potential for diverse applications.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

We put forward a novel technique to enhance the accurateness of urban land cover classification in satellite imagery by fusing the strengths of PBBO (Particle Swarm Optimisation and Biogeography-Based Optimisation hybrid algorithm), ABC/BBO (Hybrid Flower Pollination by Artificial Bees and BBO), and FPAB/BBO.

Based on the data presented in Table 3, we can conclude that our suggested strategy successfully classified urban pixels with a high precision. 90 out of 128 urban pixels were identified as such accurately, while two were misclassified as being rocky and 36 as being barren. Interestingly, no urban pixels were misclassified as water. This indicates how well our method works at accurately identifying urban areas in satellite imagery in comparison to other land cover types. Our suggested method provides a reliable and accurate solution for classifying urban land cover by integrating the mutually reinforcing strengths of both algorithms.

Dataset

In this research, the dataset we choose has selected locations with diverse land cover traits, including barren areas, vegetation, rocky areas, urban areas, and water. The dimensions of the satellite picture used for analysis were 548 pixels wide by 474 pixels high. We used sophisticated techniques to group the land cover and provide a categorized image by utilizing a variety of bands, including RGB (RED, GREEN, AND BLUE), green, MIR (MIDDLE INFRA-RED), RS1(RADAR SET1), RS2 (RADAR SET2), NIR (NEAR INFRA-RED), and DEM (DIGITAL ELEVATION MODEL). The reliability and preciseness of the land cover classification have been greatly improved by the addition of these bands and the DEM data.

The categorized graphic offers insightful information about the distribution and features of various land cover categories in the targeted areas. An in-depth comprehension of the dynamics and patterns of the land cover is made possible by the thorough study of the different bands and the inclusion of the DEM band.

Figure 1 depicts several satellite image bands that were utilized as the study's input

Figure 1 Band Satellite Image of Alwar Region.

Kappa Coefficient

A statistical metric used to evaluate the level of agreement between two raters or classifiers in categorical classification tasks is the kappa coefficient[1][7], at times referred to as Cohen's kappa. The kappa coefficient has a range of -1 to 1, with values nearer 1 indicating a higher level of agreement than would be predicted by probability alone. Quantifying the consistency between hand annotations and automatic classification outcomes is a typical procedure in image classification evaluations. A strong acceptance shown by a high kappa coefficient, points to the efficiency and dependability of the classification system.

$$\hat{k} = \frac{N \sum_{i=1}^r x_{ii} - \sum_{i=1}^r (x_{i+} \cdot x_{+i})}{N^2 - \sum_{i=1}^r (x_{i+} \cdot x_{+i})}$$

Equation 1

- r = total number of rows in the error matrix
- x_{ii} = the number of observations in the ith row and ith column (which is on the major diagonal)
- x_{i+} = total of observations in row i
- x_{+i} = total number of observations in column i
- N = total number of observations included in the matrix.

Overall accuracy

The overall accuracy of the proposed approach must be evaluated during the photo classification process to make sure the accuracy of the outcomes. The reference data and the categorization outcomes are compared category by category using the widely used error matrix in remote sensing [8]. The total accuracy gives a measure of the method's effectiveness by assessing the agreement between the assigned classes and the anticipated feature classes.

For analyzing the classification performance, additional indicators can be considered in addition to the total accuracy. These metrics comprise the producer's accuracy and the user's accuracy, which both quantify the likelihood that a pixel labeled as a given feature class belongs to that class. Producer's accuracy evaluates the likelihood of accurately identifying a certain feature class.

The ratio of correctly classified observations to all observations is used to calculate the classification's overall accuracy. This accuracy metric [9], written as "O," is determined by adding together all the values along the error matrix's major diagonal (which represents the correctly categorized observations), dividing by the total number of classifications, and then taking the result. This metric offers a thorough evaluation of the proposed method's overall performance in precisely allocating pixels to their appropriate feature classes in the categorized image.

Table 1 Error Matrix after implementing PBBO hybrid algorithm for Satellite Image Classification

	Urban	Vegetation	Water	Barren	Rocky	Total
Urban	148	0	0	5	0	153
Vegetation	1	161	0	0	0	162
Water	0	0	74	0	0	74
Barren	10	0	0	62	0	72
Rocky	0	0	0	0	101	101
Total	159	161	74	67	101	562

Table 2 After using the Fusion of Biogeography-based optimization and Artificial Bee Colony

	Urban	Vegetation	Water	Barren	Rocky	Total
Urban	113	0	0	4	0	177
Vegetation	1	108	0	0	0	109
Water	0	0	68	0	0	68
Barren	26	0	0	59	0	85
Rocky	0	0	0	0	96	96
Total	140	108	68	63	96	475

Table 3 Error Matrix of Satellite Image Classification of Alwar Region using Hybrid FPAB/BBO

	Urban	Vegetation	Water	Barren	Rocky	Total
Urban	89	0	0	35	2	126
Vegetation	12	137	0	1	0	148
Water	0	0	71	0	0	71
Barren	87	2	0	104	17	211
Rocky	0	10	0	28	181	219
Total	188	149	71	168	200	775

Figure 2 Comparing the original (on the left) and classified (on the right) alwar images using the hybrid PBBO method.

Figure 3 Using Fusion of Biogeography-based optimization and Artificial Bee Colony algorithm compared the original alwar image (left) and classified alwar image (right).

Figure 4 Comparing the original (left) and classified (right) alwar images using the Hybrid FPAB/BBO biogeography technique.

Figure 5 Comparison of Kappa coefficients of several algorithms

Figure 6 Comparison between various algorithms' overall accuracy

IV. Result Discussion

The result analysis of the research focuses on assessing the performance of three algorithms: FPAB/BBO, ABC/BBO (Hybrid Flower Pollination by Artificial Bees and BBO), and PBBO (Particle Swarm Optimisation and Biogeography-Based Optimisation hybrid algorithm[10]). Based on their kappa coefficient values—0.9600, 0.917, and 0.67927, respectively—these algorithms were evaluated.

Figure 2-4 illustrates how these algorithms were applied to the Alwar 7-band image and displays the resulting categorized images. The categorized photos' color-coded representation enables clear visualization of the many land cover types, including barren areas, vegetation, rocky areas, urban areas, and water bodies.

Figure 5 examines the values of the kappa coefficients to illustrate how well the algorithms functioned. The kappa coefficient for the PBBO method, which is 0.9600, is the foremost, demonstrating a high degree of agreement between the classified results and the reference data. With a kappa coefficient of 0.917, the ABC/BBO [10] algorithm performs admirably, while the FPAB/BBO

method has a lesser coefficient of 0.67927. A graphic illustration of their accuracy is also shown in Fig. 6. The greatest accuracy value, 97.69, is attained by the PBBO method, exhibiting a high degree of accuracy in classifying the various types of land cover.

The results analysis demonstrates the PBBO algorithm's superior performance with the highest kappa coefficient and highest accuracy, exhibiting its efficacy in correctly categorizing land cover categories in the Alwar picture dataset.

V. Conclusion and Future Scope

In conclusion, this study compares three cutting-edge nature-inspired algorithms for extracting terrain features from satellite images: PBBO (Particle Swarm Optimisation and Biogeography-Based Optimisation hybrid algorithm), ABC/BBO (Hybrid Flower Pollination by Artificial Bees and BBO), and FPAB/BBO (Flower Pollination by Artificial Bees and Biogeography-Based Optimisation hybrid algorithm). The study includes metrics like accuracy and the kappa coefficient to determine how well different algorithms operate.

The comparison analysis's findings demonstrate that the PBBO algorithm, with a kappa coefficient of 0.9600 and an accuracy value of 97.69, performed the best altogether. This technique develops a more effective and dependable optimization strategy for categorizing satellite images by combining the strengths of Particle Swarm Optimisation (PSO) and Biogeography-Based Optimisation (BBO).

Overall, the comparative study shows that these naturally inspired algorithms can advance terrain analysis and assist precise and effective decision-making in a variety of applications. The results of this study progress the field of satellite image categorization and shed light on the advantages and disadvantages of the examined algorithms. To improve these algorithms' effectiveness in certain situations or extend their use to new domains, future studies can examine improvements and changes to them.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lillesand, T.M., Kiefer, R.W. and Chipman, J.W. (2003), "Remote Sensing and Image Interpretation", Fifth Edition, Wiley & Sons Ltd., England, pp.586-592.
- [2] Kundra, H., Panchal, V.K., Singh, K., Kaura, H., & Arora, S. (Volume 4, Issue 1). "Extraction of Satellite Image using Particle Swarm Optimization". *International Journal of Engineering (IJE)*, 86.
- [3] Arora, P., Kundra, H., & Panchal, V.K. (2012). "Fusion of Biogeography based optimization and Artificial bee colony for identification of Natural Terrain Features". *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)*, 3(10)
- [4] Harish Kundra and Dr. Harsh Sadawarti, "Hybrid Algorithm of CS and PSO for Natural Terrain Feature," *Research Journal Of Information Technology*, 2015.
- [5] Simon, D. (2008), "Biogeography-based Optimization", in *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 12, No.6, IEEE Computer Society Press. pp. 702-713.
- [6] J. Kennedy, R. C. Eberhart, and Y. Shi, "Swarm Intelligence", Morgan Kaufmann Publishers, San Francisco, 2001.
- [7] Omkar S.N., Kumar Manoj, Muley Dipti (2007), "Urban Satellite Image Classification using Biologically Inspired Techniques", in *IEEE International Symposium on Industrial Electronics(2007)*, IEEE Computer Society Press, pp. 1767 – 1772.
- [8] Ralph W. Kiefer, Thomes M. Lillesand, "Principles of Remote Sensing", 2006.
- [9] R. Congalton, "A review of assessing the accuracy of classification of remotely sensed data," *Remote*, vol. 37, pp. 35-46, 1991.
- [10] Ma, H. (2009), "An analysis of the behavior of migration models for Biogeography-based Optimization", Submitted for publication.
- [11] Sowmya, D. R., Deepa Shenoy, P., & Venugopal, K. R. (2017). Remote sensing satellite image processing techniques for image classification: a comprehensive survey. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 161(11), 24-37.
- [12] Muresan, O., Pop, F., Gorgan, D., & Cristea, V. (2006, July). Satellite image processing applications in MedioGRID. In *2006 Fifth International Symposium on Parallel and Distributed Computing* (pp. 253-262). IEEE.
- [13] Asokan, A., & Anitha, J. (2019, February). Machine learning based image processing techniques for satellite image analysis- a survey. In *2019 International conference on machine learning, big data, cloud and parallel computing (COMITCon)* (pp. 119-124). IEEE.
- [14] Karnieli, A., Gilad, U., Ponzet, M., Svoray, T., Mirzadinov, R., & Fedorina, O. (2008). Assessing land-cover change and degradation in the Central Asian deserts using satellite image processing and geostatistical methods. *Journal of Arid Environments*, 72(11), 2093-2105.
- [15] Goel, L., Gupta, D., & Panchal, V. K. (2012). Biogeography and plate tectonics based optimization for water body extraction in satellite images. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Soft Computing for Problem Solving (SocProS 2011) December 20-22, 2011: Volume 2* (pp. 1-13). Springer India.

